

to identify good sources of resistance.

This report covers material tested in the Experimental Sub-Station Huarangopampa-Bagua (5° 35' lat. S., 78° 30' long. W) in 1978, 1979 and 1980. Of the 17 lines and varieties chosen for each test, 10 were selected from trials in Bagua, Yurimaguas, and Tingo Maria from 1968 through 1978 and the remaining 7 were obtained from IRBN-75, which was tested during 1976 and 1977 in the same 3 sites.

Low natural infection at the seedling stage prevented clear differentiation of the materials for resistance to leaf blast. The severity of the blast attacks at the panicle stage, however, (26% in Minabir 2 in 1978 and 70% in Fanny in 1979 and 1980) made it possible to single out the resistant materials Colombia I, C46-15,

and Tetep. These three varieties kept their resistance to leaf blast over several years and have been the most consistently tolerant in the field.

Colombia I and C46-15 had relatively good yielding potential despite their low tillering capacity. Tetep and C46-15 are tall and have lodging tendencies.

Their poor plant type should be considered if they are to be used as parents. Colombia I also is resistant to the virus disease hoja blanca and is convenient to use as a resistance source in Bagua and Jaen, where blast and hoja blanca are cyclicly epidemic.

A second group of good materials — IR1544-238-2-3, IR1416-1-42-2-3-3, and Tadukan — have shown acceptable agronomic characteristics, but are not as stable in reaction to blast as Colombia

I, C46-15, and Tetep.

IR1544-238-2-3 and IR1416-142-2-3-3 have good yield potential, dwarf plant type, and intermediate reaction to hoja blanca but have shown susceptible reactions to leaf blast. Tadukan has low yield potential, tall plant type, and intermediate reaction to hoja blanca. It has been more consistent in its resistance at both seedling and adult stages.

The rest of the rices tested showed an unstable capacity to withstand the pathogenic variability of the fungus. P545-5-22-3-5-2-2, Carreon, and Dissi Hatif, particularly, gave variable reactions. However, the same variability of the fungus imposed the use of different sources of resistance in the breeding for blast-resistant varieties. ■

Rice materials selected for resistance to *P. oryzae* in infection beds at Yurimaguas, Bagua, and Tingo Maria

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The materials tested in infection beds by the PNA (Rice National Program) consist of rices selected in the breeding program, those tested for blast resistance, PNA promising lines, and those introduced from abroad (International Rice Research Institute, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, etc.). The rices that showed blast resistance after several tests are retested and analyzed for their general reaction, reaction by locality, consistency of reaction, source of resistance used, etc.

This report includes the rices with outstanding performance during the periods 1968-72 and 1974-78, during which more than 16,500 rices were tested. It also includes the best materials in three localities.

In 1968, a strong program for rice varietal improvement started in Peru. In the first testing period (1968-72), most of the blast-resistant rices were materials introduced mainly from IRRI. IR480-5-9-2, IR532, and Tetep were used as res-

istance sources. Their progeny performed well in the second testing period (1974-78).

Of the rices ranked outstanding in the second period, 63% were from Peru, 27% from Colombia, and 10% from IRRI. These rices should be further tested for consistency of blast resistance. Among the selected material, five lines were IR480-5-9-2 derivatives, two were Tetep derivatives, two were PI 184675

derivatives, and one was a Colombia I derivative.

The PNA 12-24 group of resistant lines (6 lines), which are progeny of IR8/ Apura, are especially interesting. During the 1969-72 period in the same test localities, IR8 was moderately resistant to moderately susceptible to blast and Apura was consistently moderately resistant. The latter reaction should be defined and studied carefully. ■

Rice cultivars found resistant during a tungro epidemic

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Tungro virus disease appeared in epidemic form in Bihar in October 1980. Of 150 rice cultivars screened in six trials, only 4 were found highly resistant: IR38, IR2863-38-1, C190-1, and C183-1. BIET 281, Borogar 5, BR 1-91-6, 62-31, 7551 G-5, BR34, BR9, Parwapankh, and 64-117 were tolerant. The susceptible cultivars included Jaya, Pankaj, Biplab, T141, Intan, IET5656, IET6710, IR2050-78-1-3, and Kencanna. ■

Donors of brown spot resistance in the Indian Punjab

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The 570 IET (Initial Evaluation Trial) entries of rice received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project were screened for reaction to brown spot *Helminthosporium oryzae* in the field during 1980 kharif at the PAU Rice Research Substation, Gurdaspur. The entries were grown in 2 rows, 5 m long. Fertilizers were applied at 100-50-50 kg of N, P₂O₅, and K per hectare. The disease was scored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale, 3 months after transplanting. Two

Table 1. Donors of brown spot resistance in the Punjab, 1980 kharif.

IET No.	Designation	Source	Disease score ^a
7366	RNRO 1429	T. Hamsa/ Rasi	1
7367	RNR 27033	(T712/TNI)//HR 35	1
7343	KAU 23372	MN 54-42 mutant	3
7349	Co 32-20-66	-	3
7353	TNAU 13932/2	-	3
7364	RNRO 1446	T. Hamsa/ Rasi	3
7368	RNR 36718	(GEB 24/Sigadis)//(IR8/RNR 8102)	3
7417	R243-3041	IR7516(IR2071-625-1-252/205-3-521-3-3)	3
7497	CR294-28-1	(IR20/Zenith)// Malagkit Sungsong	3
7513	HPU5048-Pep 9-1B	JC 98/Kulu	3
7547	RP1442-2-2-3-5	Rasi/ K 46-15-B ₂	3
7145	CR263-889	T 141/Baok/T 141	3
6978	CR141-5036 CRRP5	(N22/TN1)//(T90/IR8)	3
7261	RP897-3790-30-1	Rasi/Mettasanna	3
6151	CR141-60-58-2-295	(N22/TNI)//(T90/IRS)	3
6686	IR42 (IR2071-586-5-6)	IR2042/CR 94-13	3
7291	PY 1	Ponni/IR8	3
-	Susceptible check7		

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9.

Table 2. Distribution of scores of resistance donors of brown spot of rice at PAU Rice Research Sub-Station, Gurdaspur, Punjab.

Score ^a	Leaf area infected	Resistance donors	
		Number	Percent
1	Less than 1%	2	0.35
3	1-5%	15	2.63
5	5-25%	467	81.93
7	25-50%	79	13.86
9	More than 50%	7	1.22

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

entries were scored resistant; 15 were moderately resistant (Table 1). The distribution of scores is in Table 2. The resistant and moderately resistant donors are being used in Punjab breeding programs. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Gall midge infestation in a monthly-planted trial

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A 10-m² plot of BG34-8 rice variety was transplanted on the first of each calendar month beginning in March 1977 and ending in February 1979 at Batalagoda. Infestation of gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* was assessed by counting the infested hills in the total area planted at 3, 4, and 5 weeks after transplanting. After each count the galls were removed to avoid subsequent recounting.

The total number of hills sampled and the total infested hills at 3, 4, and 5 weeks after transplanting were used to calculate the percentage of gall midge infestation for 3 particular planting dates. Gall midge infestation was bimodal with a major peak in the December planting and a minor peak in the June planting. Furthermore, data on the mean rainfall for the 2 years show that the infestations peaked 2 months after the peak rainfall (see figure). These findings are being used to plan field screening tests such as the International Rice Gall Midge Nursery and the Gall Midge Biotype study. ■

Gall midge infestation and rainfall at Central Rice Breeding Station, Sri Lanka.

Chemical differences in rice varieties susceptible or resistant to gall midge and stem borer

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Gall midge *Orseolia (Pachydropis) oryzae* and yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* are two major internal feeder

pests of rice. Varietal differences in resistance to these pests have long been observed. To understand the mechanism of resistance, we undertook biochemical studies of selected resistant and susceptible varieties.

Because the gall midge attacks the vegetative shoot apex and the stem borer attacks the stem, 1-cm-long vegetative shoot apices and 2.54-cm-long